

NAWRIZBAY TAWMURATOV IS A MAN WHO DEDICATED HIS LIFE TO DEFENDING THE PEACE AND SCIENCE OF THE COUNTRY

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There are different ideas about life. Long-lived people have experienced that it is too short, and if it is only a tuft of hair, then from a philosophical point of view, life is identified with matter without head or legs. In any case, according to the sages, a life is like a hotel where one spends the night. After all, is a child born to experience life's precious moments?

In our article, we will talk about the life of Nawrızbay Tawmuratov, a veteran of the Internal Affairs Department of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, a retired lieutenant, a lawyer who contributed to Karakalpakstan, candidate of historical sciences.

Nawrızbay Tawmuratov was born in March (Nawrız) in 1931 in a village near Tillakol, one of the paradise lands of Karakalpakstan. The child born into the Tawmurat family was named Nawrızbay because he was born shortly after Navruz traditional meal. In his autobiography, which tells about his life, Tawmuratov

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the life and activities of Nawrızbay Tawmuratov, who was engaged in research on the history of the Department of Internal Affairs in Karakalpakstan and dedicated almost his entire life to this field, as well as his scientific services.

recalls that in the post-war years (in 1948) the fishery in Karakalpakstan was well developed, and he gradually began to gain fame by working as a "receiver" of fish caught from fishermen.

In 1952, after successfully passing the exams, Nawrızbay Tawmuratov enrolled as a cadet in the secondary special two-year militia school under the Ministry of Internal Affairs located in Tashkent. N. Tawmuratov studied at this educational school with Usnatdin Utemuratov, Rajapbay Khasanov, Oldash Karasaev, Sarsenbay Sharipov.

In 1954, Nawrızbay Tawmuratov brought a secondary special police training institute diploma from Tashkent to Karakalpakstan. Initially, Tawmuratov was hired as a senior duty inspector in the internal affairs department of Nukus. In 1956, Tawmuratov was demoted to the position of senior operational representative of the Nukus Ministry of Internal Affairs. During

this time, Qalimov, who held this post, demanded and received rice from the Koreans. Koreans complained against Qalimov. This incident causes Qalimov to be fired. Because of this incident, Qalimov was fired and N. Tawmuratov, who previously worked as an inspector on duty, then started working as an operational representative of DFPSP since 1956.

In his autobiography, Nawrizbay Tawmuratov remembered that he got married in 1957 to a girl named Rakhiyma, who lived on Frunze street, Chimbay chayxana settlement, Nukus city. At that time, Rahiyma was studying at the institute, while Nawrizbay was working as an inspector of GDFPSP at the police station of Nukus city.

At the beginning of 1962, N. Tawmuratov's workplace was changed. He says about himself this: "Since the beginning of 1962, the jobs of all the employees of the GDFPSP in the republic have been changed. U. Utemuratov was transferred to the Khojeli district police department as the head of the police department, and I was transferred to the Kungirat district police department as the chief operative representative of the police department". Before the change, Tawmuratov had to choose between Kungirat and Amiwdayra districts. With the advice of Borisov Mikhail Savelevish, who worked as the head of the political department in the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, he went to work in the Kungirat district DFPSP department.

Tawmuratov arrived in Kungirat district in May 1962. From the day he arrived, he began to get acquainted with the conditions of the district. On those days, Tawmuratov talked with the head of the police department of Kungirat district,

Ermakbay Emlikbergenov, about the work that needed to be done in the district. In the end, at the suggestion of Emlikbergenov, he agreed to start work on the former Sverdlov state farm. At that time, Tilew Mamitov was working as a regional representative of this state farm. Together with Tilew Mamitov, Tawmuratov went to the Sverdlov state farm on horses.

When Tawmuratov was working in the city of Nukus, he often remembered Borisov's advice, which caused him to move to Kungirat district. On the way to Kungirat, the head of the personnel department told Borisov Tawmuratov that most of the robberies in Kungirat district are in the field of cattle breeding, and warned that investigations should be started in this area. Having listened to this advice, Tawmuratov decides to start work on the Sverdlov state farm in Kungirat district with crimes in the field of cattle breeding.

By the decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Council of the USSR dated

February 22, 1964, Kungirat district was reorganized, the center of which is the city of Kungirat. By the joint decision of the Karakalpakstan Regional Committee of the Karakalpakstan Oblast and the Council of Ministers of the Soviet Socialist Republic of Karakalpakstan on March 16, 1964, which was related to the organization of Kungirat district as a new district, the police department of Kungirat, which was part of the Khojeli district Soviet executive committee of the deputies, was dissolved. Instead, a police department was established within the Kungirat District Soviet Executive Committee of People's Deputies. On April 4, 1964, the QQASSR MPOP (Ministry of Public Order Protection) related to the establishment of the

Kungirat district police department confirmed the staff of the Kungirat district police department at 27 people, and with this order, N. Tavmuratov of the Kungirat district was appointed deputy head of the police department for operational affairs. On February 5, 1964, by decision of the Council of Ministers, the first construction of the 7th compressor station was started on the Ustirt Plain, and the urban settlement of Ustirt "Komsomolek of Ustirt" was built in Caracal on the service of the Bukhara-Uralgas Highway Karakalpakistan ASSR was established. In February of the same year, QQASSR MPOP was instructed to open an operational police station in the village. On July 7, 1964,

according to the order of the MPOP of QQASSR, one operative representative, one regional representative, GAI officer and rank-and-file police officers were allocated to the police station of the Kungirat district police station on the Ustirt plain. According to the order of the JTQM of Uzbekistan on May 25, 1965, Nawrizbay Tavmuratov was appointed as the first deputy of the head of the police department of Kongirot for operational affairs and the head of the police department of Komsomolek village in Ustirt. Thus, N. Tavmuratov became the deputy leader and the head of the village department, and he went to work once or twice a week.

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